

INTERNALIZATION OF RELIGIOUS MODERATION VALUES IN THE SHARIAH ECONOMIC SYSTEM IN HALAL UMKM THROUGH SHARIAH FINANCING PRODUCTS

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ABSTRACT

This study aims to internalize the value of religious moderation in the Islamic economic system in Halal MSMEs through Islamic financing products. Religious moderation in Islamic economics refers to a balanced and proportional approach to integrating Islamic religious principles with economic aspects. The impact is to create an economic system that is by Islamic teachings and also considers the realities and economic needs of the community. These principles must be translated wisely and precisely according to local needs and conditions. The results of the discussion of this study are the internalization of the value of religious moderation in the Islamic economic system in Halal MSMEs through Islamic financing products which include 9 important values, namely: humanity, public welfare, fairness, balance, obedience to the constitution, national commitment, tolerance, non-violence, and respect for traditions (local wisdom). The implication of this research is to know the underlying concepts in internalizing 9 important values that can contribute to the progress of the Islamic economic system, especially in Indonesia. Internationally, this is in line with the achievement of the Sustainability Development Goals (SDGs) in 2030.

Keywords: *Religious Moderation, Islamic Economics, Halal Micro, Small and Medium Enterprises (MSMEs), Islamic Financing*

I. INTRODUCTION

In practice, religious moderation promotes awareness of human rights, religious freedom, and equality among religious communities, as well as fostering the ability to appreciate differences and engage in good dialogue (Tarigan, 2022). Meanwhile, the concept of Islamic Economics covers various types of economic activities, including banking, investment, insurance, trade, and finance. Overall, religious moderation in Islamic economics combines financial, social, and moral aspects in running a balanced and sustainable Sharia-compliant business. This is done to gain profits and embrace social responsibility as citizens and Muslims (Novitasari, 2019).

Halal MSMEs in Indonesia have great potential in the global market, especially among Muslim consumers who are increasingly aware of the importance of choosing halal products. To increase the competitiveness of Halal MSME products, the Regional Government (Pemda) and various financial institutions have provided various supports and facilities, such as training, financing, and halal certification, so that it is expected to help improve product quality and expand the market (Rohimah et al., 2023). One of the problems faced is that most Halal MSMEs in Indonesia have not received sharia financing from Islamic banks. This is due to the lack of public understanding of small business financing products (KUR Syariah) in Islamic banking. Also, Islamic banks rarely socialize their Sharia financing products to Halal MSMEs in rural areas. This results in most of these Halal MSMEs receiving financing from conventional banks whose transactions are not based on Sharia principles (Afandi, 2021). Therefore, the purpose of this study is to internalize the value of religious moderation in the Sharia economic system in Halal MSMEs through Sharia financing products, especially in Indonesia, and generally in the international world.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 Religious Moderation

The concept of religious moderation is an approach that emphasizes the importance of maintaining balance and a moderate attitude in practicing religious teachings, especially in the context of a pluralistic and multicultural society. Religious moderation means avoiding extremism or fanaticism and choosing a middle path in practicing religious teachings, while still paying attention to the principles of goodness, tolerance, and equality of human rights. Religious moderation is necessary because it has several important benefits in maintaining harmony, tolerance, and harmony among various religious groups and beliefs (Fitria, 2023).

Religious moderation is an approach or attitude that aims to promote dialogue, understanding, and tolerance between individuals or groups who have different beliefs or religions. The main goal of religious moderation is to avoid conflict, hatred, and disagreement that may arise due to religious differences. In the context of religious moderation, individuals or groups tend to find common ground, understand differences, and work together to overcome common problems that are not related to religion. This involves various actions, such as participating in interfaith dialogue, celebrating religious festivals together, respecting the beliefs of others, and finding ways to collaborate on things that benefit society as a whole (Sulaiman, 2021). Religious moderation also avoids religious extremism and intolerance and supports religious freedom and human rights. This can create a more peaceful, inclusive, and harmonious environment where people from different religious backgrounds can live side by side without serious conflict. In addition, religious moderation can also involve an approach to formulating public policies that respect religious diversity and ensure that the rights of all citizens are respected without discrimination based on religion or belief (Noor, 2022).

2.2 Sharia Economy

Sharia Economy is an economic system based on the principles of Islamic law or Sharia (Dewi et al., 2023). Its goal is to promote justice, community empowerment, and general welfare, and ensure that economic activities are carried out by Islamic values. Some of the main principles of the sharia economy include (1) Prohibition of usury/interest; (2) Prohibition of maisir/gambling; (3) Prohibition of gharar/uncertainty; (4) Ethical risk and financial management; (5) Distribution of social justice; (6) Productive assets and based on real value; and (7) Fair and transparent transactions. Sharia economics generally focuses on the principles of ethics, justice, and sustainability in various aspects of the economy. This system views the economy as an integral part of the religious and social life of Muslims and tries to avoid social and economic imbalances that can occur in conventional economic systems (Walyoto, 2022).

Sharia economics covers various sectors, including banking, finance, investment, trade, insurance, and other sectors. Sharia financial institutions such as Islamic banks, Islamic microfinance institutions, and Islamic capital markets operate by these principles. Sharia economics involves various financial and banking instruments that are by Islamic principles, such as mudarabah (partnership), musharakah (jointly), sukuk (Islamic bonds), and takaful (Islamic insurance). (Yafiz, 2022)

2.3 Halal Micro, Small and Medium Enterprises (MSMEs)

Halal MSMEs are types of small and medium enterprises that focus on producing or providing products and services that comply with halal principles in Islam. Halal MSMEs have several characteristics, including: first, compliance with halal principles, namely Halal MSMEs comply with halal guidelines and rules set out in Islam. This means that the products or services produced must be free from ingredients that are considered haram (not allowed) in Islam (Rofika et al., 2023). Second, halal certification. Many Halal MSMEs are trying to obtain official halal certification from an authorized institution to determine the halalness of a product. This certification can provide consumers with confidence that the products they buy have met the established halal standards (Pradesyah, 2023). Third, sustainability. Halal MSMEs often prioritize ethical values in their business, which are in line with Islamic principles. This can include environmental sustainability, social welfare, and fair business practices. Fourth, target market. Halal MSMEs generally focus on Muslim consumers who prioritize the consumption of halal products. However, halal products can also attract non-Muslim consumers who are looking for products that are considered more moral or of better quality (Ahyar, 2019).

The fifth is innovation. Halal MSMEs can develop innovative products that comply with halal principles, combining technology and creativity to meet the needs of an increasingly growing market. Sixth, Community Empowerment: Halal MSMEs can be a source of livelihood for local communities and help drive the economy in certain areas. When looking at Halal MSMEs, it is important to remember that the nature of "halal" involves more than just materials and production processes.

Marketing, promotion, and the entire product life cycle must also comply with halal principles (Amani, 2022).

2.4 Sharia Financing

Sharia financing is a form of financing or funding based on Sharia principles in Islam. Sharia principles aim to create transactions that are fair, ethical, and according to Islamic teachings. In the context of Islamic financing, several main principles must be followed, including (Budianto, 2022):

First, the principle of prohibition of usury (interest). Usury, or interest, is prohibited in Islam. Therefore, in Islamic financing, there is no payment or receipt of interest. Second, the principle of profit sharing (Mudharabah and Musyarakah). In Islamic financing, the concept of profit sharing is applied. Mudharabah and musyarakah are two types of financing based on this principle. Mudharabah is a form of cooperation between the capital owner (shahibul maal) and the business manager (mudharib), where the profit is shared according to the agreement. Musyarakah is a form of cooperation between two or more parties to generate profits, with the distribution according to the proportion of each party's capital contribution (Gozali et al., 2023). Third, the principle of fair sale and purchase (Murabahah and Salam). This principle involves fair and transparent sale and purchase transactions. Murabahah is a sale and purchase transaction with a profit that has been agreed upon in advance. Salam is the purchase of goods in cash with delivery made in the future. Fourth, the principle of prohibition of speculation and usury. Sharia financing also avoids speculation and practices that harm one of the parties in the transaction.

Fifth, the principle of social responsibility and business ethics. Sharia financing encourages high social responsibility and business ethics, including avoiding investment in sectors that are forbidden by Islamic teachings, such as alcohol, gambling, and products containing pork (Angraini, 2022). Forms of sharia financing can include various products and services, such as housing financing, vehicle financing, investment financing, and other financial products. Financial institutions that provide Sharia financing usually follow the guidance and fatwas of scholars and authorized Sharia supervisory bodies. In practice, sharia financing aims to provide an alternative that is by Islamic values for those who want to avoid conventional transactions that conflict with sharia principles (Sari, 2022).

III. METHODOLOGY

UIN Mengabdi 2023 activity with the theme "Internalization of Religious Moderation Values in the Sharia Economic System through Sharia Financing Assistance for Halal MSMEs in Pasuruan Regency." This activity involved lecturers from various faculties at UIN Maulana Malik Ibrahim Malang, including the Faculty of Tarbiyah and Teacher Training and the Faculty of Economics, as well as students.

This activity uses the Participation-based Community Service (PAR) method and involves the Halal MSME community in Penambangan Village, Balongbendo District, Sidoarjo Regency. The following are the steps used in the activity: (1) MSME Empowerment: The PAR method empowers MSMEs by involving business owners

and community members in decision-making and implementation of actions. With active participation, MSMEs have a greater opportunity to grow. (2) Halal Product Development: MSME activities focus on producing products to Islamic religious principles. The PAR method helps MSMEs develop products that meet halal requirements, from raw materials to the production process. (3) Quality Improvement: Through the PAR process, MSMEs can improve the quality of products and services based on community feedback and participation. This involves identifying problems, planning improvements, implementing actions, and evaluating results. (4) Implementing Islamic Economic Principles: The PAR method helps MSMEs integrate Islamic economic principles into business operations, including transparent and fair financial management. (5) Disseminating Knowledge: The PAR method is used to disseminate knowledge about Islamic economic principles and Halal business practices to MSME owners and the community. This helps MSMEs operate better and have a positive impact on the local community and economy. (6) Increasing Community Awareness: The PAR method aims to increase community awareness about the importance of supporting Halal-based MSMEs and the Islamic economy.

This is done by building a better understanding of the benefits of the Islamic economy and Halal products. Thus, this activity does not only focus on research but also aims to create real changes in the situation of Halal MSMEs and the Islamic economy in the area.

IV. RESULTS AND ANALYSIS

4.1 Community Service Location Overview

The UIN Mengabdi activity in Penambangan Village, Balongbendo, Sidoarjo aims to build partnerships with communities near industrial areas. MSMEs in Pasuruan are growing rapidly, with more than 255,000 business units recorded in 2023, with a growth of 2.06% per year. Halal MSMEs in Pasuruan have great opportunities in the global market, with support from the government and financial institutions to improve product quality and a wider market.

4.2 Current Conditions of Assistance

Halal MSMEs in Penambangan Village, Sidoarjo, face problems with sharia financing. Most MSMEs there have not received support from Sharia banks due to a lack of understanding of the Sharia KUR product. Several factors that influence this situation are increasing awareness of MSMEs regarding Islamic economic principles, the development of Sharia financial products, government support, the need for training and education, and technological innovation in the Sharia financial industry. These efforts are expected to help Halal MSMEs obtain appropriate sharia financing and support their business growth.

4.3 Expected Conditions

In 2022, UIN Mengabdi focuses on community service to create a smart village (Qoryah Thoyyibah) in the service area. They provide sharia financing assistance to

Halal MSMEs in Penambangan Village, Sidoarjo Regency. The objects of assistance include village officials, cooperative and Sharia bank employees, Halal MSME owners, and the community who want to know more about Halal MSMEs. The main objective of the program is to increase community knowledge about religious moderation in the Sharia economy in Penambangan Village.

4.4 Description of Community Service Activities

This activity is carried out in the following stages: (1) Coordination with the UIN Maulana Malik Ibrahim Malang Research and Community Service Institute regarding preparations for the implementation of Community Service. (2) Coordination with the RT administrators and local MSME heads as well as data collection (pre-test) in the form of a questionnaire to determine how far the assisted objects understand the concept of religious moderation in the Sharia economic system in Halal MSMEs. (3) Providing basic counseling to subjects regarding the basic concept of religious moderation in the Sharia economic system in Halal MSMEs. (4) Socialization and education to assisted objects regarding the importance, placement, supervision, and implementation of internalization of religious moderation values in the Sharia economic system in Halal MSMEs through Sharia financing assistance in Penambangan Village, Balongbendo District, Sidoarjo Regency. (5) Monitoring and evaluating the implementation of activities that have been carried out and providing access to sharing and counseling between assisted subjects through Forum Group Discussion (FGD) activities, both online and offline. (6) Submission of financing products in the form of basic materials for each MSME product that participates in the assistance.

4.5 Relatedness (Parties Involved and Forms of Involvement)

There are several agencies/companies/communities related to this community service, namely: first, the Pasuruan Regency Cooperative and Micro Business Service. The duties of this service include being responsible for developing MSMEs in their area, which can be done by providing guidance, training, and access to the resources needed, as well as helping to empower the community's economy through providing business capital assistance, developing business networks, providing access to markets and business mentoring. Second, the Pasuruan Regency Halal MSME Community in increasing public awareness and understanding of the importance of choosing and consuming halal products. Third, Bank Syariah Indonesia (BSI) Pasuruan Regency, which is one of the banks operating in Indonesia with Sharia principles. Sharia financing at BSI is one of the products offered by this bank to meet the financial needs of the community by sharia principles.

4.6 Implementation of Community Service Activities

First, providing basic counseling to subjects regarding the basic concept of religious moderation in the Sharia economic system in Halal MSMEs.

Figure 1. Providing Basic Counseling

Second, socialization and education to assisted objects regarding the importance, placement, supervision, and implementation of internalization of religious moderation values in the sharia economic system in Halal MSMEs through sharia financing assistance in Penambangan Village, Balongbendo District, Sidoarjo Regency.

Figure 2. Socialization and Education

Third, monitor and evaluate the implementation of activities that have been carried out and provide access to sharing and counseling between assisted subjects through Forum Group Discussion (FGD) activities, both online and offline.

Figure 3. Monitoring and Evaluation

Fourth, the delivery of financing products in the form of basic product materials for each MSME participating in the mentoring.

Figure 4. Financing Product Delivery

4.7 Demographics of Mentoring Participants

Participants of the 2023 UIN Mengabdi Qaryah Thoyyibah community service program in Penambangan Village, Balongbendo District, Sidoarjo Regency, based on gender, namely: 5 men and 20 women.

4.8 Discussion of Scientific Studies

4.8.1 The Importance of Internalizing Religious Moderation Values in the Sharia Economic System

Religious moderation is needed in the Sharia economic system for several main reasons, including maintaining balance. The Sharia economic system aims to create a balance between economic, social, and spiritual aspects in people's lives. Religious moderation helps prevent extremism or religious fundamentalism that can disrupt this balance. Then, avoiding exploitation, namely religious moderation helps avoid

exploitation in economic transactions. By implementing Sharia principles based on justice, transparency, and honesty, the Sharia economic system prevents abuse and exploitation that can harm the weaker party. Another reason is the added value, namely religious moderation ensures that the ethical and moral values of religion are maintained in economic transactions. This gives a more dimension to economic activity, ensuring that profits are obtained in a halal manner and accordance with religious values.

In addition, regarding the reduction of systemic risk, namely religious moderation can help reduce systemic risk in the economic system. By avoiding unethical or questionable practices, such as excessive speculation or market manipulation, the Islamic economic system can reduce the likelihood of a damaging economic crisis. Then, for sustainable development, namely, religious moderation supports sustainable economic development. Sharia principles that encourage fair distribution of wealth, environmental protection, and productive investment help create a more sustainable and future-oriented economy. Furthermore, to prevent corruption, namely the principles of Islamic economics, such as transparency and integrity, help prevent corruption. By avoiding corrupt practices that damage the economic system, religious moderation helps maintain justice in the distribution of wealth. Others for community development, namely religious moderation can support the development of a balanced and harmonious society. The principles of Islamic economics help empower the economy of society, reducing social disparities, and promoting economic inclusion.

By implementing religious moderation in the Islamic economic system, economic goals that include justice, sustainability, and balance can be achieved while respecting the underlying religious values.

4.8.2 Internalization of Religious Moderation in the Islamic Economic System

The placement of religious moderation in the Islamic economic system involves harmonization between Islamic economic principles and religious values. The goal is to create an economic environment that is by Islamic teachings and also maintains a balance between economic and spiritual aspects.

One of the first steps is to provide education and awareness to the community about the principles of Islamic economics and how to apply them in everyday life. This can be done through seminars, classes, Friday sermons, and other media. Then, the government or responsible institution needs to formulate policies that reflect the principles of Islamic economics. This can include the establishment of an institution that oversees the implementation of these principles, as well as regulations that support economic transactions based on sharia. In addition, business ethics in Islamic economics are highly emphasized. Business actors are expected to run their businesses honestly, fairly, and responsibly. They are also expected to avoid practices that are prohibited in Islam such as *riba* (interest), *gharar* (excessive uncertainty), and *maisir* (gambling). Next, provide various forms of sharia financing such as *mudharabah*, *musharakah*, and *murabahah* that are by the principles of Islamic

economics. This allows entrepreneurs and individuals to obtain funds in a halal manner and accordance with religious values.

Development of waqf (charitable assets) and sadaqah (donations) for social and economic purposes. These funds can be used to support projects that benefit the community, such as infrastructure development, education, and health. Then, the Sharia economic system must also focus on poverty alleviation and economic empowerment of the weak. Instruments such as zakat and infaq can be used to help those in need. In addition, developing Sharia financial institutions such as Sharia banks, Sharia insurance, and Sharia capital markets. These institutions operate based on Islamic economic principles and can provide alternatives for people who want to transact according to sharia. Eighth, it is important to have a strong monitoring mechanism to ensure that economic transactions and practices are by sharia principles. If there is a violation, fair law enforcement must be applied.

Halal product development needs to be carried out to ensure that the products produced and sold are by halal standards. This includes aspects of food, pharmaceuticals, and cosmetics, as well as ensuring that the production and distribution processes are by religious principles. And also, developing a community-based economy through the development of micro, small, and medium enterprises (MSMEs) that are by Islamic economic principles. This can help empower the local economy and distribute wealth more evenly. It is important to remember that the implementation of religious moderation in the Sharia economic system requires cooperation from various parties, including the government, society, business actors, and scholars. This also requires a balance between religious and economic aspects, as well as adaptation to developments in the era and technology.

4.8.3 Monitoring the Internalization of Religious Moderation in the Sharia Economic System

In the Islamic economic system, religious moderation and its monitoring are the shared responsibility of the Muslim community. However, several entities or groups have an important role in monitoring religious moderation in the context of Islamic economics, including scholars. Scholars, who are Islamic religious scholars who have in-depth knowledge of Islamic teachings, have a key role in monitoring religious moderation. They can provide guidance and fatwas (legal opinions) related to the economic aspects of Islam to ensure that economic practices are by religious principles. Then, religious institutions, namely religious institutions, such as religious science assemblies, fatwa councils, and other religious bodies, have a role in providing guidance related to economic practices that are by Islamic values. They can also monitor economic and financial practices to ensure there are no violations of religious principles.

Next is the government. Governments in countries with an Islamic economic system also have a responsibility to oversee religious moderation in the economy. They can issue policies and regulations that support economic practices that are by Islamic principles, such as the prohibition of usury (interest) and economic practices that create injustice. Fourth, society. Muslim society also has an important role in

overseeing religious moderation in the Islamic economic system. Individuals can make economic choices that are by religious values, such as investing in halal businesses and avoiding transactions that conflict with Islamic principles. The last is Islamic economic organizations. There are Islamic economic organizations that focus on developing and promoting economic practices that are by Islamic teachings. They can provide guidance, provide training, and support the development of economic models that are on religious principles. With the synergy of these various entities and groups, religious moderation in the Islamic economic system can be better maintained, so that economic practices can be in line with religious values and principles of justice. There are 9 important values in religious moderation, namely: humanity, public welfare, fairness, balance, obedience to the constitution, national commitment, tolerance, anti-violence, and respect for tradition (local wisdom).

4.8.4 Internalization of Humanitarian Values in the Sharia Economic System in Halal MSMEs through Sharia Financing Products

Internalization of humanitarian values in the Sharia economic system refers to the process of uniting and applying moral principles, ethics, and concern for humanity in the implementation of an economic system based on Islamic principles (Sharia). Humanitarian values in this context refer to respect for the dignity and human rights of each individual, as well as efforts to create prosperity for society in a just and sustainable manner.

4.8.5 Internalization of Public Benefit Values in the Sharia Economic System through Sharia Financing Products

Internalization of public welfare values is a very important concept in the Sharia economic system. It refers to the process by which individuals, communities, and economic institutions adopt and apply values that promote shared prosperity and social sustainability in economic decision-making. This principle underlies the way the Islamic economic system operates and differs from conventional approaches that may be more focused on personal gain.

4.8.6 Internalization of Fair Values in the Islamic Economic System through Islamic Financing Products

Internalization of fair values is the process by which a value or principle is adopted and applied personally and collectively by individuals or society. Fair values in the context of the Islamic economic system refer to the principles of justice and equality that are the basis of an economic system governed by Islamic principles. The Islamic Economic System is based on the teachings of Islam and the Quran. One of the central values in this economic system is the value of fairness or justice.

4.8.7 Internalization of Balanced Values in the Islamic Economic System through Islamic Financing Products

Internalization of balanced values in the Islamic economic system refers to the concept in which the principles of Islamic economics or sharia are reflected in the economic

actions and behavior of individuals, institutions, and society as a whole. This concept is based on the belief that economic success must be accompanied by moral and ethical accuracy, as well as respect for Islamic principles.

4.8.8 Internalization of Constitutional Values in the Islamic Economic System through Islamic Financing Products

Internalization of constitutional values in the Islamic economic system refers to the process in which the principles of Islamic law (sharia) are applied consistently within an economic framework that is by the values of a country's constitution. In this case, "constitutional" refers to respecting and following the basic laws of the state as stipulated in the constitution, while "sharia economic system" refers to an economic model that is based on Islamic principles.

4.8.9 Internalization of National Commitment Values in the Sharia Economic System through Sharia Financing Products

Internalization of national commitment values in the sharia economic system refers to the integration and adoption of national values in economic practices based on sharia economic principles. National values include aspects such as love of the homeland, unity, cooperation, and the spirit of nationalism. In the context of Sharia economics, this can be interpreted as the application of Islamic economic principles that are in line with national values and the spirit of patriotism. Islamic economic principles, such as social justice, sustainability, and equitable distribution of wealth, can contribute to building a more inclusive and equitable economy by the spirit of nationality.

4.8.10 Internalization of Tolerance Values in the Sharia Economic System through Sharia Financing Products

Internalization of tolerance values in the Sharia economic system refers to the process of adopting and implementing the concept of tolerance as an integral part of economic principles based on Islamic teachings. The value of tolerance in this context refers to respect, recognition, and acceptance of differences in society, especially in the economic context. In the Sharia economic system, several basic principles must be followed, such as the prohibition of usury (interest), gharar (excessive speculation), maysir (gambling), and transactions involving haram goods or services. However, in internalizing the value of tolerance, the application of these principles must be carried out by considering the differences in culture, background, and religious views that are diverse among members of society.

4.8.11 Internalization of Anti-Violence Values in the Sharia Economic System through Sharia Financing Products

Internalization of anti-violence values in the Sharia economic system refers to the process by which principles that oppose acts of violence, exploitation, and unfair treatment are applied and deeply internalized in an economic context based on Sharia principles in Islam. The Sharia economic system has a philosophical and ethical

foundation that prioritizes justice, humanity, and sustainability, and condemns all forms of actions that harm individuals or society in general.

4.8.12 Internalization of the Principle of Respect for Tradition (Local Wisdom) in the Sharia Economic System through Sharia Financing Products

Internalization of the Principle of Respect for Tradition (Local Wisdom) in the Sharia Economic System refers to efforts to incorporate local or traditional values and practices into an economic framework based on the principles of Sharia in Islam. This principle aims to respect and apply elements of local culture and tradition in economic operations that are by Islamic teachings. The Sharia Economic System is based on guidelines taken from the Quran and Hadith, as well as broader Islamic principles. Some of the main principles in the Sharia Economic System include the prohibition of *riba* (interest), *gharar* (excessive uncertainty), *maysir* (gambling), and the prohibition of investment in *haram* (forbidden) industries. However, in its implementation, this system must be able to adapt to local culture and traditions to create harmony and continuity.

4.8.13 Follow Up (Program Sustainability)

Here are some sustainable activity programs that can be carried out in this program:

- (1) Education and Training: Organizing training, seminars, and workshops involving religious figures, economists, and academics. They can talk about the principles of Islamic economics and how to apply them moderately and inclusively.
- (2) Panel Discussion: Holding a panel discussion involving religious leaders, economists, and Islamic economics practitioners. This discussion can discuss how to overcome potential conflicts between the principles of Islamic economics and the principles of religious moderation.
- (3) Social Media and Online Campaign: Building a campaign through social media and other online platforms to spread information about the relationship between religious moderation and Islamic economics. This content can be in the form of articles, short videos, infographics, and podcasts.
- (4) Islamic Financial Training: Organizing Islamic financial skills training for the community, including an understanding of financial instruments that are by the principles of Islamic economics.
- (5) Interfaith Partnerships: Building partnerships between different religious communities and Islamic financial institutions. This can help build mutual trust and a better understanding of religious values and Islamic economics.
- (6) Research and Publication: Supporting in-depth research on how religious moderation and Islamic economics can synergize. The results of this research can be published in the form of reports, scientific articles, or books.
- (7) Development of Educational Materials: Creating educational materials that can be used in schools or community training. These materials should highlight the importance of tolerance, interfaith cooperation, and the principles of moderate Islamic economics.

- (8) **Online Communities:** Building online communities where interested individuals can share experiences, exchange ideas, and discuss issues related to religious moderation and Islamic economics.
- (9) **Social and Humanitarian Activities:** Organizing social and humanitarian activities that involve the participation of various religious communities. This can help strengthen relationships between religious communities and build cooperation to promote moderate Islamic economic values.
- (10) **Awards and Recognition:** Providing awards to individuals, groups, or institutions that have contributed to promoting religious moderation and the implementation of a balanced Sharia economy.

V. CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATION

Based on the results of the community service above, it can be concluded as follows: first, the importance of internalizing the value of religious moderation in the Sharia economic system is to maintain balance, avoid exploitation, provide added value, reduce systemic risk, sustainable development, prevent corruption, and community development. Second, the placement of internalization of religious moderation values in the Sharia economic system to provide education and awareness, policy formulation, business ethics, Sharia financing, poverty alleviation, Sharia financial institutions, supervision and enforcement, halal product development, and community-based economic development. Third, internalization supervision is carried out by scholars, religious institutions, government, society, and Islamic economic organizations. Fourth, 9 important values in the internalization of religious moderation in the Sharia economic system in Halal MSMEs through Sharia financing, namely: humanity, public welfare, fair, balanced, constitutional, national commitment, tolerance, anti-violence, and respect for tradition (local wisdom).

Recommendations and Suggestions

Community service activities related to religious moderation in the Sharia economic system can have a positive impact on promoting the values of tolerance, inclusiveness, and justice in Sharia economic practices. Here are some recommendations and suggestions for carrying out these activities:

- (1) **Education and Training:** Provide education and training programs for the community to understand the principles of Sharia economics in depth. This can include holding seminars, workshops, and training in various aspects of Sharia economics, as well as how to integrate the values of religious moderation into daily economic practices.
- (2) **Counseling and Campaigns:** Hold counseling and campaign activities to increase understanding of the importance of religious moderation in Sharia economics. This campaign can be carried out through social media, lectures, posters, and other educational materials.
- (3) **Positive Case Studies:** Share successful examples of individuals or companies that have implemented the principles of religious moderation in Sharia

economic practices. Tell these inspiring stories to inspire others to apply the same values.

- (4) **Interfaith Partnerships:** Form partnerships with other religious groups to jointly educate the public about religious moderation in the context of Islamic economics. This will strengthen interfaith cooperation and increase understanding across faiths.
- (5) **Research and Publication:** Research how religious moderation can be applied to Islamic economic practices. The results of this research can be published in the form of articles, books, or reports so that they can be accessed by the general public and Islamic economics practitioners.
- (5) **Business Model Form:** Develop a business model that combines the principles of Islamic economics with the values of religious moderation. For example, a business that promotes inclusivity and social welfare through its business practices.
- (6) **Entrepreneurship Training:** Provide special entrepreneurship training to groups in need, such as youth, women, and marginalized communities. In addition to understanding the economic aspects, this training can also include ethical aspects and values of moderation in business.
- (7) **Partnership with Universities and Religious Institutions:** Collaborate with universities and religious institutions to develop a curriculum or educational program on religious moderation in Islamic economics.
- (8) **Socialization of Moderation Principles:** Socialize the principles of religious moderation in an integrated manner in the curriculum of religious education and Islamic economics at various levels of education.
- (9) **Monitoring and Evaluation:** Always monitor and evaluate the effectiveness of this community service activity. By understanding the impact generated, you can continue to improve and develop better strategies.

Remember that community service is a long-term effort. With commitment, hard work, and good cooperation, you can create a significant positive impact in promoting religious moderation in the Sharia economic system.

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